

The Impact of Interdisciplinary Approach on Curriculum Design: IB-MYP

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Abstract:

This report aims to explore the impact of interdisciplinary perspective in educational settings as an important tool to enhance curriculum development. The literature review evaluates the benefits of integrated disciplines as a form of unified learning that tackles the depth of understanding in a classroom setting whilst outlining some of the outcomes that could emerge from integrated learning in the shape of collaboration, creativity, and lateral thinking to solve complexity. Equally, it aims to persuade the management team to implement ongoing professional development throughout the academic year and allocate weekly slots for planning to increase the level of collaboration amongst teachers. This would ensure dedicated sessions are scheduled to design interdisciplinary units that fulfil the recommendations outlined by the International Baccalaureate (IB) for Middle Years Programme (MYP) to enrich the experience of students to gain a holistic approach to learning. The report also provides an insight into curriculum design and development when addressing some of the social, economic, political and cultural aspects that have played a significant role in impacting curriculum reform.

Introduction:

When talking about curriculum development, one may refer to an improvement to the current programme of study that may benefit from further refinement and amelioration, which eventually can be introduced in the form of a change that mirrors the society's set of values, one that cannot resist to remain static but continuously adapt and evolve (Primrose & Alexander, 2013). As with Primrose and Alexander, Welsh suggests that 'Interdisciplinary theory engages in questions of value and judgements' (pp.22, 2011), hence there is a need to align curriculum design with the community's set of principles to attain a sensible approach that would meet the community's need.

It is therefore crucial to observe and analyse the behaviour, reaction, and routine of learners to identify the appropriate change required to establish an efficient and well-grounded scheme of learning and assessment that would define the goal and objectives of this change to help ensure every student is equipped with the necessary transferable skills that would match the complexity of the contemporary world they live in (Tyler, 2013). Equally, placing learners' interests and needs at the heart of curriculum design should be considered as a paramount factor during this stage of its development to sustain a continuous support for all learners (Seaman & Nelsen, 2011).

As per IB, middle schools bear the responsibility to provide the students in each of the academic years of the programme with a minimum of one interdisciplinary unit that includes a combination of no less than two subjects (IBO, 2022). By doing so, learners would be able to connect their understanding to tackle complex tasks to meet the initial level of recommendation outlined by the IB. This would also ensure a greater level of planning is put in place to promote interdisciplinary learning across MYP to create further opportunities for collaborative and integrated learning, which allows for the schools to meet the required standard of practice to secure a greater fulfilment of the IB programme. Hence, both, middle and senior school management teams are encouraged to emphasise the implementation of interdisciplinary learning as a practice across all the group years in MYP, to enrich the learning experience of students by allowing them to gain a horizontal and vertical curriculum understanding of unified disciplines in a progressive manner.

Review of literature

Dewey states that 'the child and the curriculum are simply two units which define a single process (pp. 11, 1902). In a world that is constantly changing, Dewey recognised experimentalism as the ultimate teaching philosophy to provide students with a holistic learning approach to nurture their passion and allow them to develop and grow as a globally minded citizen, hence **a need for a curriculum reform to unify classroom practice with the current global transitions to tackle social structure and encourage independence within democracy** (Holt, 2020). Dewey's position on curriculum reform remains relevant today, as Ralph Tyler equally shares his view while highlighting his supports on the impact and benefit of students' learning experiences to become an integral part of curriculum design (Tyler, 2013). There is no doubt that Dewey's publication at the beginning of the 20th century turned out to be fruitful and brought a breath of fresh air into the field of education on how to view the curriculum which inspired many of his contemporaries such as William Kilpatrick to focus on project method as child centred approach to curriculum development; and Franklin Bobbitt, who went into dividing the curriculum into the skilled gained from the social experiences of an individual and the training gained in the classroom to complement and refine those skills through the application of scientific principles to solve practical issues of schooling (Eisner, 1967).

Tyler takes this a step further and defines **the purpose of education as a way of solving the current problems identified by our sociologists, hence the need to avoid duplicating those skills and experiences elsewhere to create a meaningful programme of study**, while taking into account the various aspects that may impact the curriculum design, starting by the role of the society, the subject specialist, and the students themselves, with the addition of the school's philosophy, mission

and vision which place a great emphasis on their stand in the community and its citizens (Tyler, 2013). Soto argues that 'curriculum development is a broad and complex process' (pp. 1129, 2015). This statement reveals Soto's assertion to reflect on the multiple variations and interpretations found amongst scholars, philosophers, sociologists, and politicians on how the term 'curriculum' has been defined, used, and referred to, which connect us to the core of this report, and how to analyse further the role of interdisciplinary and its relation to our society and system of education. According to Welsh, interdisciplinary thought is a response to the demands of society, seeking to solve "real world problems" (pp. 34, 2011).

Interdisciplinary studies has positioned itself as an innovative approach to comprehending, navigating, and transforming knowledge (Welsh, pp. 1, 2011). There is no doubt that if one is to assess the content and the structure of the IB curriculum to strongly agree with Welsh's statement on the position interdisciplinary learning has established in shaping its programme of study.

When inspecting the sketches of Leonardo DaVinci, there is an undeniable link between drawing, science, and writing, yet each of these elements preserve a level of admiration on its own, however, the blend of the three components results in an interdisciplinary approach allowing for each of the elements to be enhanced further by the presence of the other component, leading to the creation of a new, and powerful outcome (Ulbricht, 1998). James A Beane, who is a prominent scholar in the field of curriculum integration, emphasises in his work that interdisciplinary boundaries are not fixed, but rather fluid, and in most cases connect to other disciplines and subject matter organically, leading to establish an activity or a project, based on an interdisciplinary approach, hence a need to maintain a flexible approach during the process of planning (Beane, 1995).

Interdisciplinary studies allow for a natural approach to knowledge to establish a constrictive perspective to reasoning while provide a contemporary explanation to the question of epistemology (Welch, 2011). Gusdorf states that the need for interdisciplinary has been reflected in epistemological writing ever since the origin of Western science (pp. 580, 1977). Yet, if one is to analyse this statement from an ontological perspective to help decide on whether in-depth writing has been produced to address the weaknesses found in interdisciplinary implantation to equip educators to overcome its limitation, then the answer is no (Bhaskar et al, 2018). On the other hand, the past decades have shown a rapid increase in adapting interdisciplinary studies as an innovative approach to learning, however the concept of unified knowledge has been portrayed ever since the ancient Greek ideal (Burton, 2001).

Klein argues that 'the roots of concept lie in a number of ideas that resonate throughout the modern discourse – the ideas of unified science, general knowledge, synthesis and the integration of knowledge (pp. 19, 1990). Bhaskar et al tackles the interdisciplinary perception further by highlighting the difference between the observed world and the real world while adapting a philosophical approach based on critical realism to develop a unified educational knowledge (Bhaskar et al, 2018). **One should note the manner of how the concept of interdisciplinary has been structured is not solely based on ideas but rather the way those ideas were placed to shape the curriculum to avoid any limitations that may cause overspecialisation to restrict a learner to a single discipline**, but instead, explore various field of study to develop a sense of unified knowledge of disciplines (Klein, 1990). Welsh suggests that interdisciplinary mindset takes a metacognitive step beyond subjective envelopment, and in doing so attains a better vantage point for making judgments and creating knowledge (pp. 34, 2011).

According to Campbell an interdisciplinary project can be one of the most important and effective instructional vehicles teachers have for challenging their students' intellect (pp. 44, 1995). This perception of lateral thinking would allow for educators to inject critical thinking into their classroom teaching by selecting units of work that would help sustain a balance of depth and breadth across various materials of study to promote purposeful connections across disciplines (Barrett, 2007). In the MYP, students are encouraged to exhibit their level of understanding by using a collection of methods, concepts, as well as various form of communication to link two or more disciplines to exhibit an interdisciplinary perspective to allow them tackle complex issues, and in some occasions, raise a new question (IBO, 2022). According to De Greef et al 'To reach a more comprehensive explanation of complex, real-life problems, insights from several disciplines have to be reconciled and combined' (pp. 10, 2017). This level of integration would then be conceived as an approach to complexity to enhance the effectiveness of understanding to become a scheme of navigating knowledge and transferable skills (Welsh, 2011). As a result of this integration, each discipline would then be amplified and strengthened by the others to allow for creativity to emerge by generating new forms of understanding (Ulbricht, 1998). Shelter suggests that 'Interdisciplinary strategies and designs offer the most logical and feasible path for those who view the serious study of musical behaviour as critical to the future of the profession and the discipline (pp. 32, 1990). When working on an interdisciplinary unit, **it is crucial to build on students' prior knowledge to stimulate classroom learning, however, the core of any activity should be based on allowing students to experience new ways on how to apply their prior understanding and skills to embrace other disciplines, as this will help reduce any current (isolated) gaps found in the curriculum** to reach an interrelated approach to learning, with the aim to acquire new skills that would exhibit

those learning objectives across multiple disciplines (Campbell, 1995). It is equally an opportunity for those in the profession to embrace a challenge and design a multidisciplinary work scheme based on a collaborative method for learners to experience a holistic approach to education, based on an integrated prospective (Shelter, 1990).

The National Association of Secondary Schools of Principal (NASSP) highlighted in its 1998 (is this a good idea to include if it was 25years ago) report the various benefits that could be drawn from integrating learning into interdisciplinary programmes of study which include:

- Cultural integration that caters to the diversity and backgrounds of students.
- Tackling multiple styles of learning (differentiation).
- Creating a balance that blends the economic needs of students.
- Promoting inclusion in group work.
- Encouraging a sense of collaboration through project-based learning.
- Creating a sense of community amongst the teachers.
- Improving classroom environment.
- Promoting inquiry and investigating.
- Encouraging creative and authentic outcome. (NASSP, 1998 as cited in Burton, 2011).

Implementing Interdisciplinary

In 2018 the International Baccalaureate Organisation (IBO) commissioned for an external evaluation to be conducted by the Claremont Evaluation Centre (CEC) as research study on how Inter-Disciplinary Unit (IDU) were led across Middle Years Programmes (MYP) whilst visiting 27 IB Schools on site, and comparing it to the 2017/2018 MYP Teachers Survey across the globe to assess the level of collaborations, the depth of disciplinary learning and the strengths related to the skills of cross-curricular. Their report identified three categories of implementation:

Category N1: led by teachers' initiative and only affected students enrolled on those specific classes.

Category N2: Integration through topics to link two disciplines, or through assignment while completing a project.

Category N3: explicit level of planning that occurs frequently across the academic year.

The CEC's findings highlight the lack of time and the limited knowledge of teachers as the main two barriers impacting the implementation of IDU across MYP and, recommends from the leadership team to support their teachers by providing professional development, and allocating regular time slots for planning, with the addition of appointing an IDU Coordinator. The report also points out a discrepancy between the initial confidence claimed through the survey and the minimal level of integration found on site (IBO, 2020).

When considering the current hours dedicated for each MYP discipline during their initial phase of secondary learning, Arts teachers for instance are faced with a maximum number of 50 hours per academic year, which limits their ability to deliver the core syllabus of their subject and plan a comprehensive interdisciplinary unit (Interdisciplinary Teaching and Learning in MYP, 2021). Therefore when involving Arts students in an interdisciplinary activity or a project, there is a tendency that their contribution would be restricted to singing or drawing, which is usually associated with a theme inspired by historical or social events that runs in parallel with the schools current horizontal articulation of the curriculum, however, **in the eyes of certain teachers this is a comprehensive way of implementing interdisciplinary teaching to show evidence of integrated learning; this style of learning would surely create to a certain extent a connection to other disciplines, however, elements such as creativity and composition in this case are neglected and not fully stimulated** in the classroom to inject critical thinking or pursue creative ability to further energise the classroom environment (Campbell, 1995).

A level of stimulated learning may become evident through a stronger and organic connection when designing an interdisciplinary unit in MYP when additional slots have been allocated for planning and collaboration. Teachers from different fields of specialisation could then team up as a collective, select an excerpt from a theme that would embed elements of students' daily life while echoing a particular issue found in their routine or the society at large to become a pertinent and complex issue to investigate. Work such as *Midnight's Summer Dreams* by Shakespeare can be reinterpreted with a fresh and authentic approach. The final product could be outlined as students' personal project which can be presented in a form of music composition inspired by the main character or the society to display a sense of creativity; perhaps using a music instrument in a silent way in a form of an accessory of embellishment to the performance set; acting using different expressions that help brings the text and the struggle found in the society to life; translating the original text to students' regional dialects to celebrate their cultural heritage; or even considering the use of the classroom as a studio arena for film making. This would allow the teachers to collect various form of evidence during their regular interactions held in the school in various forms, such as PowerPoint presentation and regular entry journals to conduct their evaluation; in the same manner, it also provides the students with the opportunity to express their intentions and display their understanding through the three assessment criteria set by IB for interdisciplinary projects in the following way:

- **Evaluating:** this is an opportunity to allow students to reflect on their understanding to analyse the application of disciplinary knowledge and evaluate their contribution across various stages from an interdisciplinary perspective.
- **Synthesising:** in this criterion students justify how they have tackled real-world ideas and issues to create a meaningful product that would showcase their ability from an interdisciplinary approach.
- **Reflecting:** in this final stage of the project, students are expected to discuss the progress of their interdisciplinary learning and how they would apply the newly acquired knowledge in their future projects.

(Interdisciplinary Teaching and Learning in the MYP, 2021).

Interdisciplinary units within the IB frame of work provide an opportunity to reinforce the use of various concepts and global contexts to link individual subjects to achieve a fruitful level of integration that would help conceptualise students' understanding within an interconnected society (MYP Arts Guide, 2014). Hence a binary approach becomes necessary when conducting interdisciplinary units, however, **one must note that not all disciplines create a natural connection to one another to justify their depth of integration, and therefore, a meaningful outcome should be sought in the early process of planning** to establish interactive links between the subjects and the final product (Burton, 2011).

Conclusion

The report looks at various benefits of implementing interdisciplinary studies across MYP, whilst taking into account the time required for planning and designing a comprehensive work scheme by middle school teachers. Burton suggests that 'what constitutes a discipline of knowledge has much to do with the task of designing interdisciplinary programs' (pp. 17, 2001).

The unique experiences and cultural background of teachers opened the door for the term interdisciplinary to go by various names such as lateral knowledge, integrated discipline, transdisciplinary or cross-curricular to form different meanings depending on how the concept of interdisciplinary has been presented to each one of them to contextualise their understanding (Barrett, 2007). On the other hand, these multiple interpretations cause a concern around the definition of interdisciplinary to establish a clear and transparent meaning on how to approach it; even though the outcome of these characteristics emerged from engaging and debatable sessions, disparity remains prominent amongst educators (Bhaskar et al, 2018).

MYPs continue to express enthusiasm for interdisciplinary studies while facing a challenge to embed it systematically in its classroom to establish a solid frame of work that is primarily based on designing a body of knowledge in an interdisciplinary manner to effectively combine individual disciplines to help reduce any learning gaps that may impact the holistic approach of a child, hence, a need for an ongoing professional development within this area to equip teachers with the methods and standard of practice required to implement it effectively (Manlove, 2021).

Exploring various themes should be the initial stage during the planning of interdisciplinary learning to engage teachers and students on topics that may wish to investigate. Once this step has been established, each group subject would then reflect on their level of contribution to create a unified interdisciplinary unit (Beane, 1993). Schools may benefit further by establishing a system that would allow for interdisciplinary teachers to be grouped in an organised manner with their fellow workers to ensure dedicated and specific slots are scheduled for planning to encourage and ease curriculum integration, however one must consider the scale of this process on the admin team to create such a meticulous timetables that would cater for curriculum integration, especially if designed to include a wide range of disciplines (Vars, 2001).

The IB committee recognises the limited number of hours allocated for each subject group especially when it comes to those who fall under the umbrella of arts (music, drama, dance, theatre and visual art) to plan and maintain concurrent units of study across the entire academic year, hence a recommendation to use post school hours slots to engage faculty members and students who are signed up for an interdisciplinary project to benefit from further sessions to meet the aim of the course (MYP Arts Guide, 2014).

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